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Ilia Palaguta

Cucuteni-Tripolyye: ceramic assemblage, periodization, cultural development. Some general reflection

Keywords: The Cucuteni-Tripolyye culture, relative chronology, periodization, ceramic assemblage, figurines, social reconstructions.

Cuvinte cheie: cultura Cucuteni-Tripolyye, cronologie relativă, periodizare, ansamblu ceramic, figurine, reconstituiri sociale.

Ключевые слова: культура Кукутень-Триполье, относительная хронология, периодизация, керамический комплекс, статуэтки, социальные реконструкции.

Ilia Palaguta

Cucuteni-Tripolyye: ceramic assemblage, periodization, cultural development. Some general reflection

In recent decades, studies of the Cucuteni-Tripolyye culture have acquired a more multifaceted character, while it became possible to use the potential of a number of European archaeological schools to study the phenomenon of that culture. Certain aspects of the development of that culture remain debatable. The author presents for discussion a number of issues related to the further aspects of its periodization, the analysis of ceramic assemblage, the interpretation of its fine art monuments, and social reconstructions.

Ilia Palaguta

Cucuteni-Tripolyye: ansamblu ceramic, periodizare, dezvoltare culturală. Câteva reflecții generale

În ultimele decenii, studiile asupra culturii Cucuteni-Tripolyye au căpătat un caracter mai complex, în timp ce a devenit posibilă folosirea potențialului mai multor școli arheologice europene pentru a studia fenomenul acestei culturi. Anumite aspecte ale dezvoltării acestei culturi rămân discutabile. Autorul prezintă spre discuție o serie de probleme legate de aspectele ulterioare ale periodizării sale, analiza ansamblurilor ceramice, interpretarea monumentelor sale de artă fină și reconstrucțiile sociale.

Илья Палагута

Кукутень-Триполье: керамическая коллекция, периодизация, культурное развитие. Некоторые общие размышления

Исследования культуры Кукутень-Триполье в последние десятилетия приобрели более многоплановый характер, когда для изучения феномена этой культуры стало возможным задействовать потенциал целого ряда европейских археологических школ. Отдельные аспекты развития этой культуры остаются дискуссионными. Автор представляет к обсуждению ряд вопросов, касающихся дальнейшей разработки ее периодизации, анализа керамических комплексов, интерпретации памятников изобразительного искусства и социальных реконструкций

I am motivated to write this article by an environment that is not conducive to research. It is reminiscent of the events that unfolded in Europe 80 years ago and led to the situation when many of the trends emerged in the 1920s and 1930s have never got further development. It also affected the area of study of Cucuteni-Tripolyye, because many scholars of the 'interwar' generation died in the dungeons of the Gulag, Nazi concentration camps, besieged Leningrad. Therefore, I would like to have time to summarize some of the results of the study of this culture over the past three decades, so that a number of important considerations are not lost in the stream of current events that break the fate of people and break the established ties in the research community.

A significant breakthrough in the Cucuteni-

Tripolyye research occurred in the 2000s-2010s, primarily due to the development of international collaborations. This applies as well to Ukraine, and Romania, and Moldova, where research was launched jointly with specialists from Germany, Great Britain, and Poland. That made it possible to enrich the experience of field work and to expand the array of analytical methods. The results of that work have been published in the form of numerous articles, collections and scholarly monographs¹.

1. Providing a detailed bibliographic list is not the purpose of this article, but we cannot escape mentioning the works by Ukrainian researchers E. Ovchinnikov, A. Diachenko, L. Shatilo, D. Chernovol, D. Zhelaga, A. Peresunchak, M. Lobanova, Ya. Yakovishina, specialists from Moldova S. Popovich, S. Bodian, Gh. Sirbu, and M. Vasilache, as well as R. Ohlrau, and R.A. Uhl from Germany, and many others.

The Russian school of the Tripolyye studies is associated with the names of T.S. Passek (1908-1968), E.K. Chernysh (1924-2006), N.V. Ryndina (1936-2022), T.D. Belanovskaya (1918-2010), and T.A. Popova (1931-2004). At present, it is represented, in fact, by the author of this article and E.G. Starkova (State Hermitage), who work mainly with museum collections, as well as N.N. Skakun and V.V. Terekhina (IIMK RAS, St. Petersburg), who studied the Trypillia flint processing and tools. Of the Moscow specialists, one can name V.I. Balabina (IA RAS, Moscow), whose works concern small plastic items. Most likely, these specialists in Cucuteni-Tripolyye are to be the last ones here.

In this regard, the author would like to share with colleagues his reflections on a number of important aspects in the study of the Cucuteni-Tripolyye culture. All of them, one way or another, were previously touched upon in publications, but still require detailing and clarification. These are:

- understanding the principles of periodization and its correlation with the real development of culture, as well as the necessity in some adequate terminology;

- understanding the principles of formation of ceramic assemblage of settlements, a possibility of using ceramics for reconstructions of the development and spread of culture, the relationship of local formations emerging in this process, as well as the development of principles for correlating the identified parallels for reconstructing the system of interconnection of assemblages;

- interpretation of fine art monuments presented in the form of small plastic objects and images on ceramics;

- reconstruction of the processes of dissemination of settlements, integration of population groups, formation of settlements and groups of interconnected settlements, i.e. ethnohistorical reconstructions;

- identification of relationships within the entire cultural complex, both in material culture, economy, production, and coomonday life, as well as in spiritual culture, and social structures, as far as we can currently reconstruct them from material remains.

Periodization and local variants as objects for discussions

Cucuteni-Tripolyye is a complex and multi-component system of successive settlements (mostly single-layer, with a fairly short lifetime from 50-70 to 100-150 years), which developed on a vast territory covering a fairly integral expanse of the forest-steppe zone from the Eastern Carpathians to the Dnieper with an area more than 350 thousand km², for about 2000 years (according to calibrated dates, about 5000-3000 BCE). Hence the diversity of local manifestations, a complex and constantly changing system of interconnection between settlements and their groups, initiating ongoing discussions of researchers about the periodization and relative chronology of sites.

The periodization of Cucuteni-Tripolyye was worked out under the conditions of the location of the cultural area on the territory of several states and its development by researchers from various schools. The difference between the Cucuteni and Tripolyye periodizations was that Hubert Schmidt's scheme was originally based on stratigraphy [Schmidt 1932], while that one by T.S. Passek – on the classification of ceramics of one-layer sites and an attempt to build it into typological chains [Passek 1935]². In the course of comparing those scales, the gaps inevitable when summarizing studies of a vast area of the region were filled with the existing monuments [Passek 1949]. Stratigraphically, this periodization was confirmed only in the 1950s through the excavations in Polivanov Yar and Nezwysko, where the stratigraphy reflected the discontinuous usage of the site of the settlement in different periods of its cultural development. Subsequently, during the excavation of new sites, 'transitional' stages were added to it, such as Tripolyye BI-BII or BII-CI. In Romania, however, multi-layered monuments are rare; here, too, observations on the style of ceramic decoration played the main role in detailing the scheme. As a result, it is difficult for a non-specialist to understand the options for comparing these schemes.

So, the main problem is the differences in the development of ceramic traditions of local

2. The author should mention here the role of B.A. Latynin (1899-1967); in 1926-1928, he worked together with T.S. Passek, who developed the basis of that periodization. Repressed in 1935, he spent 18 years in Gulag and exile, after which he has never returned to the Trypillia theme. The manuscript of their unpublished study is stored in the Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (VUAK fund No. 586).

groups of sites, when we are faced with variations in the composition and qualitative characteristics of their ceramic assemblage. Since the systematization of the material is focused primarily on the features of ceramic decoration, the presence of several ornamental traditions in one assemblage significantly complicates the matter.

This is especially true for monuments at the 'junctions' of periods. For example, are Vasylivka and Ozheve in the Dniester basin [Shumova 1994; Zhelaga 2023] monuments of Tripollye BI? The bulk of the material here is utensils with relatively archaic relief decor (deep lines and fluting). But there is a chronological marker: pottery painted in the Cucuteni styles A-B, which forms the *terminus ante quem* for this period. So, to what stage should the monument be attributed? After the excavations in Vorniceni in Romania, which yielded a series of similar painted pottery³, it is clear that it is possible to synchronize these sites with these sites of Cucuteni A-B. Also, there is material from Brînzeni IV, genetically strongly associated with previous sites, which I initially attributed to an earlier period of Cucuteni A – Tripollye BI, but then its dating was clarified [Palaguta 2016a; Țerna, Heghea 2017]. Such cases will be repeated numerously with the study of new settlements of any periods, especially in previously little-studied parts of the range.

There are two ways in this area: to complicate the system by creating new local columns that will fit together in various ways, or to draw, on the basis of synchronisms, conditional chronological layers corresponding to the general Cucuteni-Tripollye scheme:

Precucuteni – Tripollye A
 Cucuteni A – Tripollye BI
 Cucuteni AB – Tripollye BII
 Cucuteni B – Tripollye CI
 Post-Cucuteni – Tripollye CII

The periodization scale here is just a convention, a tool that allows us to structure the material into relatively synchronous layers. Within such a 'grid-matrix', as on a squared-graph sheet of a notebook, we may depict the evolution of individual local variants and groups of sites (fig. 1). The is-

3. The full results of the excavations of this settlement, carried out in the 2000s, have not yet been published, but numerous photographs of the finds are represented in illustrated publications and on the Internet.

sue of simplifying periodization, obviously, should be left for further discussion in the research community. The language barrier, which leads to ignorance of the materials of monuments located on different banks of the Prut River, and, accordingly, to drawing the border between the Cucuteni and Tripollye cultures along modern state borders, has already been mentioned [Palaguta 2019, 30].

Here, another theoretical problem arises: how to consider Cucuteni-Tripollye – as an archaeological culture or as a cultural community?

At the level of Precucuteni-Tripollye A, there is no doubt that the sites within the entire area they occupy are so similar in the nature of the material that they represent one archaeological culture⁴. The diversity of local lines of development was clearly manifested at the beginning of the middle ('developed') stage of existing of the Cucuteni A – Tripollye BI culture. But here, according to the phases of development, 5 or 6 local variants can be distinguished [Palaguta 2016a]. The main feature is the distribution of painted pottery in the western part of the Cucuteni-Tripollye area, but, at that time, pottery with relief ornamentation is also found in the west, and painted pottery is found in the east. Recording finds of painted pottery in the eastern part of the range is often difficult due to the fact that the paint is not always preserved⁵. Thus, it is too early to talk about the identification of various archaeological cultures – Cucuteni and Tripollye – within the common area.

Differences between the sites of the extreme northeast become quite obvious (the dominance of the traditions of ceramic ornamentation with painted or relief ornaments) only at the level of Cucuteni AB-B – Tripollye BII-CI. It is difficult to draw a stable border between them because of migrations within the common area (anyway, it does not pass along the modern administrative and

4. There are different points of view on the issue whether this stage should be singled out as a separate archaeological culture [see: Ursu 2014; Chernovol et al. 2021].

5. Pottery with traces of painting on a smooth surface is also found at the sites of Precucuteni – Tripollye A. It is, in particular, in Florești I (some fragments were recorded by the author when dismantling the collection stored at the Museum of Archaeology and Ethnography of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Saint Petersburg), Bernovo-Luka, Luka-Vrublevetskaya (fig. 2). The poor state of its preservation may be due to both the peculiarities of the painting technology (composition of binders?), and the dominance of reducing firing in the ceramics manufacturing that can affect its adhesive properties.

Fig 1. Approximate scheme for the development of local groups of the early agricultural culture of the Cucuteni-Tripolnye type.

state borders). There are also assemblages where both 'western' painted and 'eastern' relief ceramics are represented (it is Racovăț on the Dniester, Vladimirovka in the Bug-Dnieper interfluvium, etc.). Are there two cultures within a community, or one, albeit with its own 'development lines' in the ceramic assemblage? And can we make justified attempts to consider the identification of cultures on the basis of differences in ceramics only, especially in the situation when these ceramic assemblages have a common origin? This issue also deserves a detailed discussion.

We can talk, obviously, about a single cultural-historical space with common genetic roots, where the principles of dissemination of population, the layout of settlements, house-building techniques, and a complex of labor tools have an undeniable similarity.

It is quite possible to consider a set of individual cultures that developed on the basis of Tripolnye-Cucuteni at the turn of the Eneolithic

and the Early Bronze Age only the final stage of their development, when the differences between different parts were reflected in the appearance of burial grounds, and in the change of the shape of vessels and their set, and in the cardinal change in symmetry of ornaments, and in the economy, and in the character and size of the settlements.

Ceramics: the set of shapes, ceramic assemblage, ornament

Despite the widespread use of radiocarbon dates, the number of which has increased by an order of magnitude in recent decades, the study of ceramic assemblages still plays a decisive role in solving the issues of periodization, building the relative chronology, and the identification of the local groupings of Cucuteni-Tripolnye sites. Ceramics is the most widespread and the most changeable material in terms of shape variations and ornamentation. A large volume of ceramic collections (usually about 20 reconstructed vessels

Fig. 2. Painted ceramics from Florești. Precucuteni II — Trypillya A phase.

from a dwelling and hundreds or thousands of fragments), as well as a fairly diverse set of shapes of vessels and their ornamentation varieties, on the one hand, provides more opportunities for analysis and comparison of settlement materials, on the other hand, makes the ceramic assemblage of this culture quite difficult to handle. This, perhaps, is one of the reasons why many collections have not been fully introduced into the research circulation for decades, although, heated discussions flare up about the belonging of the monument to one or another period or local group on the basis of individual published samples.

Archaeological and functional assemblages are somewhat different things: they are either the entire volume of ceramic material, or a set of vessels that could be used simultaneously [Palaguta, Starkova 2021]. From the point of view of a set of shapes and ornamental varieties, they correspond to each other, but the quantitative composition of these varieties in the layer of the settlement is different. The reason lies in the lifespan of vessels of various shapes and purposes: for a bowl or a drinking goblet, this is usually about a year, and for a storage vessel, it can reach 5-6 years or more. Accordingly, in a fragmented state, vessels with a shorter lifespan will prevail in the settlement layer.

In Cucuteni-Tripolyye we are dealing with a ceramic assemblage where vessels are usually decorated according to their shape. Therefore, the percentage ratio of vessel fragments with different ornamentation can give only the ratio of different shapes with different life spans. It is not correct to compare assemblages on the base of the ornaments exclusively. Similarities and differences between them appear only in the course of comparing series of vessels of

the same shape. To represent these series, one needs a continuous drawing of the material with a graphic reconstruction of shapes, a comparison of shapes and ornaments in order to understand the general structure of the assemblage; unfortunately, such analysis is missing in many works.

We should also note that against the background of the development of the classification of ceramics according to its shapes and peculiarities of its ornamentation, the study of technology and manufacturing technique of that ceramics and its ornamentation is still not sufficiently included in the procedure of studying the ceramic assemblage. Ceramic technology is usually still understood as the composition of the ceramic body. However, it characterizes only one stage in the production of ceramics, which include: 1) preparation of raw materials; 2) modeling and molding; 3) ornamentation before firing; 4) drying and firing; 5) ornamentation of the vessel after firing and its preparation for use. The study of each of the links in this technological chain becomes the basis of the principle of *chaîne opératoire* — sequences or chains of operations. The term itself was borrowed from the study of flint industries, although its principles were laid down more than half a century ago in the famous work by A.O. Shepard 'Ceramics for Archaeologists' [Shepard 1956].

All links of this process are interconnected: when the master prepares the molding mass using the available raw materials, he already imagines what and how he will make from it. Therefore, the choice of its components will depend on the fact how the product is to be subsequently molded (for example, by knocking out or cutting off excess clay), firing it (in an oxidizing or reducing environment), etc.

The ideas of Gottfried Semper (1803-1879) play an important role in understanding the processes of shape creation and its connection with materials and technologies; Semper proceeded from the fact that “the change of things, their typology is completely subordinate to the peculiarities of the development of the technical culture of the team, manifested in organized handicraft production practice”, that is, “all the changes that occur with things, with their formal and functional features, completely depend on the creative ideas of a person and on the techniques used by him in the process of organized labor activity” [Kozhin 2011, 13-14]. That is, the form of an artifact is determined both by its function and by the influence of several groups of factors: materials and technologies, natural and social conditions, the requirements of a certain customer, and the skills of the performer [Semper 1884]. These factors also lay out the foundations of the style, where symmetry, proportionality, and direction form the basis of shaping the objects [Semper 1860, XXIV-XLIII].

Four original ‘technical activities’, types of crafts, are designated by Semper in accordance with the properties of the main natural materials. This is textile art (braiding and weaving); the art of ceramics; tectonics (both wood construction and a system of metal structures); stereotomy (construction of stone, as well as carving in various materials) [Semper 1860, 9-12]. All of them are interconnected. Therefore, Semper's ideas make it possible to identify traces of the presence of non-ceramic prototypes in the shapes and ornaments of ceramics and to perceive it in the context of the entire complex of braided, textile, wood, and other products made from non-preserved organic materials, as well as the connection of its technologies with metallurgical production, processing of solid materials, etc. Based on these connections, for instance, the ‘technical ornament’ becomes clear: the reproduction of a pattern and texture of the surface of non-ceramic products or disappeared structural details (the semantic components associated with them, respectively, should also change).

Another important aspect in terms of the formal study of ceramic ornamentation is the analysis of the types of symmetry according to which the compositions are built. The experience of its application allows us to designate global changes in culture. Thus, changes in the symmetry of or-

namental compositions during the Tripollye CII period provide another reason to distinguish it from the proper Tripollye culture as it is [Starkova 2021]. And the differences in symmetry between the ornaments of the Linear Pottery culture and Cucuteni-Tripollye are a serious argument against the idea of their genetic connection [Palaguta, Starkova 2021a].

Symmetry analysis involves the study of the visual perception of symmetry. But due to the ‘reversibility’ of ornaments (especially its abstract geometric forms), it is not always clear what is considered the background, and what is an array of actual figures in the frames of the ornament. Therefore, another promising topic is the reconstruction of the process of ornamentation, marking the ornament and the sequence of applying the elements and motifs of the ornament [Palaguta 2020].

In both cases, complex observations are required, as well as a rather laborious graphic reconstruction of the compositions. However, taking into account these aspects of ceramic production, we get a possibility to identify ceramic traditions more reasonably and to reconstruct links between them on the sufficiently strong evidence base, not on their external similarity only.

The problem of the semantic interpretation of ornaments has already been numerously touched [Palaguta 2016b; Palaguta 2023]. It is not possible to see any ‘ornamental texts’ and signs of ‘proto-writing’ in ornaments, but I consider it quite promising to study ornaments from the point of view of their evolution as a sign-signal and index, where the composition as a whole matters. The meaning of individual elements or motifs can be considered either in the context of the whole composition, or as ‘markers’ of masters who perform the composition according to their own rules and with their own preferences for these or those elements. Works by T.M. Tkachuk are interesting in this regard from the point of view of the presence of characteristic ornamental elements (‘signs’) in certain groups of dwellings, which indicates their connection with a possible grouping of the population of the village [Tkachuk, Mel'nik 2000, 152-153, 205, fig. 18].

The appearance of images against the background of ornaments – episodic at first, then more or less regular – turns the ornament itself into a frame for them. The ‘fashion’ for anthropo-

morphic and zoomorphic images appears in the Siret-Prut interfluvium, somewhere at the level of the Cucuteni A-B/2 phase (Traian – Dialul Fîntînilor) and then spreads during the Cucuteni B – Tripol-lye CI period to other parts of the range along with carriers of the ‘western’ tradition of painted pottery [Palaguta 2012, 248-253].

Visual art: problems of interpretation

Myth-making in the interpretation of art objects of ancient agricultural societies has been started to develop actively since the 1960s thanks to the efforts by Academician Boris Rybakov, who actively searched for the origins of Slavic paganism [Rybakov 1964; Rybakov 1981]. The logic of such constructions is simple: the cults of fertility should dominate among the ancient farmers. It could be used to explain both ornaments and plastic objects. A similar approach was used by Marija Gimbutas, who had her vision of Eastern European archaeology [Gimbutas 1956]⁶, as well as the experience in identifying “ancient symbolism in Lithuanian folk art” [Gimbutas 1958]. After her own research of Neolithic monuments in the Balkans, she created an artificial construct “The Civilization of the Goddess” [Gimbutas 1974]. The dominance of those ideas was supported by the high scholarly status of the creators of myths. Those ideas were debunked only in the 1990s. [Meskell 1995; etc.], but certain trends in such a ‘mytho-poetic’ interpretation of Trypillian-Cucuteni art have been preserved in popular non-fiction literature until the beginning of the 21st century. [Rakhno 2012].

Does it make sense to create new myths? And how to avoid further myth-making when interpreting the material?

Obviously, it is necessary to build a logical research procedure: from empirical observations to the subsequent synthesis of their results, induction and deduction.

It should include:

- consideration of objects and their assemblages, their description and systematization by form (formal analysis), the scale of products, the degree of their preservation and fragmentation, manufacturing techniques and technology;

6. In 1960, B.A. Latynin wrote in his comments on the margins of that book: “At least one thought of his own!”, “Yes, this is a complete thoughtless compilation!”, “Yes, this is just a ‘comics book’ on archaeological topics! (and in general, even though it’s a ‘comics’, but carefully made!)”.

- studying the peculiarities of the archaeological context, reconstruction of possible ways of exhibiting and storing plastic objects;

- identification of assemblages and connections of objects in them;

- iconography studies, including comparison of ways of depicting details, attributes, reconstruction of possible non-surviving elements, and compositions by linking products in assemblages, etc.;

- the interpretation itself: reconstruction of meanings and imagery based on comparisons, but comparisons not on the basis of direct analogies, as in the ‘comparative method’ (for instance, by J.J. Fraser) that is “merely a bringing together of items which appeared to have something in common” – “an illustrative rather than a comparative” [Evans-Pritchard 1965, 10], while the analysis of the ‘behaviour’ of similar products in other cultural environments and the identification of structural parallels – similar functionalities and contexts, on the basis of which one can build more or less reliable reconstruction.

As an axiom, one can choose a common feature of visual objects: each of them has its own narration – comments that accompanied it and made by the performer, users, and viewers. Such text, of course, has not come down to us, but iconography may indicate it. For figurines, these are the posture, attributes, features of the molding of individual parts of the body, the quality of surface finishing, decoration, holes for attaching missing parts, specifics of damage, etc. It should be borne in mind that such commentary text may change, despite the fact that it may include relatively stable formulas and metaphors⁷.

Without any doubt, these objects are related to religion and cult practices, but above all, they are **works of fine art**, where standard elements of forms and techniques are combined with the results of the individual creativity of a concrete performer.

No matter how dominant was the sphere of the sacred in the life of an ancient (or modern) person⁸, any action in this area – a rite or ritual,

7. A set of stable metaphors used in poetic texts is represented, for example, in “The Language of Poetry” by Snorri Sturluson (1178-1241) [Sturluson 1995].

8. Discussions about some special ‘primitive thinking’, the presence of which was argued for by L. Lévy-Bruhl in the 1920s and 1930s. can only be considered in the context of historiography [Evans-Pritchard 1965, 88-91]. Today’s events clearly demonstrate that archaic ‘mythological thinking’ can dominate in the modern ‘rational’ world.

sacrifice, etc., – it refers not only to the sacred sphere, but also performs a certain social function, acts as a communicative act [Gell 1998]. Often we forget about this and consider this area as something self-sufficient and exclusive. In fact, in any archaic (and not only archaic) communities, this action plays a certain role in the construction of the collective, the formation of ties between its members.

The object of art is the embodiment of the realm of the imaginary. And we mean not only any abstract, but also concrete images. The standardization of execution techniques and forms creates an apparent monotony, but one should not forget about the attributes that have not been preserved: paint, clothes, decorations that complemented the figures.

The study of iconography plays an important role in the interpretation of plastic arts. Identification individual groups of features in the process of systematization of the material (classification) give a basis on which it is possible to distinguish a series of products depicting one character or a group of close characters. Formal analysis is the foundation of such study. It should be followed with iconographic analysis, identification of compositions, and analysis of the context⁹.

In the interpretation of small plastic objects of any culture, the area of analogies denotes a circle of small sculpture, corresponding to the 'chamber' scale of human hands (as opposed to monumental sculpture, oriented towards public demonstration). A significant part of this array appears in the same context as in Cucuteni-Tripollye: it is directly connected with the dwelling (although among the plastic objects, in general, there are figurines found in burials, and votives associated with sanctuaries and temples, denoting already other functional areas). Thus, in this area, one can start to search for structural parallels, including those where characters are described in the same 'domestic' context in historical sources or by ethnographers [Palaguta 2022a]. This very similarity of contexts makes us, when interpreting the Cucuteni-Tripollye figurines, turn to the Ancient Roman Lares and Penates, the biblical Teraphim, the Katsina of the Pueblo people of America, the anthropomorphic Ongons of some peoples of Siberia, etc.; it is the plasticity that was associated with the scale of human hands.

9. Such a principle of consideration was indicated, for example, by R. Leasure [Leasure 2011].

So, among the early Trypillian anthropomorphic figurines, a number of stable types can be more or less clearly identified:

— thinkers, a rare type, indicating southern connections; the only figurine is from Tirpesht;

— figurines with a vertical hole at the bottom, which, obviously, was made to fix such figurines on a vertical wooden pin;

— 'standing' figurines; some of them are with their hands raised up (similar to the figurines of the Gumelnița culture);

— 'semi-sitting' figurines with pronounced steatopygia, which, according to A.P. Pogozheva [Pogozheva 1983], take 60-80% of the total Early Trypillian objects of plastic; these very small sculptures are part of the sets, consisting of 21 figurines (fig. 3,1-2,3).

Sets of figurines provide an opportunity to identify stable compositions formed by a grouping of characters. Numerous discussions on the relationship of these sets with female fertility or their interpretation as "a council of the goddesses", unfortunately, do not come from the analysis of the material itself. Differences in the iconography of the figurines show that the sets included both female and male characters¹⁰, which raises the question of the validity of such interpretations. Some sets similar in structure continue to exist up to Cucuteni B – Tripollye CI [Palaguta, Mitina 2014; Palaguta 2016c].

The set of characters and the ways of their embodiment in sculpture is undergoing changes. The next stage, Cucuteni A-B, provides a series of figurines with holes in the shoulders and hips, which were used to fasten clothes and accessories (fig. 3,5-6), in addition to changes in the style of the figurines (spindle shape) [Peresunchak 2023]. Noteworthy, large standing statuettes appeared in the course of that period; in Păuleni-Ciuc - Dâmbul Cetății they reach the parameters of the 'cabinet sculpture' [Buzea, Kovacs 2016]. It is possible that here we are dealing with elements of the 'home altar'.

In Cucuteni A-B-B, a new trend also appears: putting figurines into models of dwellings, as well as special arrangements of figurines in vessels. Besides, in the Bug-Dnieper interfluvium, mod-

10. I would draw the attention of my fellow archaeologists to art studies, in particular, to the works by Erwin Panofsky, who developed a methodology for analyzing a work of art from its formal characteristics up to the iconography and iconology [Panofsky 1955].

Fig. 3. Figurines of Cucuteni-Tripollye culture: 1-2 – male and female figurines from the set, Poduri; 3 – figurines from Bernovo-Luka [Palaguta 2022]; 4 – model from Popudnya [Palaguta, Starkova 2017]; 5-6 – female and male figurines from Bilcze Złote [Kadrow (ed.) 2013]; 7 – zoomorphic figurine with horizontal holes in legs from Nemirov [Smirnova et al. 2018]

els of dwellings with figurines fixed in them (like the model from Popudnya; fig. 3,4) are becoming widespread [Palaguta, Starkova 2017]. They illustrate the trend towards the ‘privacy’ of the scenes, the development of a close connection between the person and the dwelling.

As a result, there are several intertwining lines of plastic usage, a plurality of characters; and that speaks on the versatility of the Cucuteni-Tri-

pollye art. Changes in the stylistics of plastic art manifest the stage-by-stage development of that culture, and changes in the iconography traced through the ‘scenes’ show us the development of ideological views directly related to the general processes in the societies and their structure.

Innovations and strategies of cultural and social development

Firstly, this is copper metallurgy, the technologies for smelting which from ores spread in the Balkan-Carpathian region in the 5th millennium BCE. One of the consequences of the introduction of copper chisels, adzes, and axes was the improvement of woodworking techniques, that expanded the base for the manufacture of more complex structures (judging by the finds of structures of wells of the culture of the Linear Pottery culture, the system of connecting parts using a groove and a spike, as well as felling log cabins, has become widespread as early as the Neolithic [Tegel et al. 2012]). Accordingly, it should have been reflected in the development of housing construction and vehicles.

The second is the use of draft animals. Their use in arable farming is evidenced with finds of Early Tripollyen plow (*ralo*) for loosening the soil, made from deer antlers [Sorochin 1991, 109-111]¹¹. The same idea lies in the construction of sledges, dozens of models of which have been found at Trypillian settlements [Balabina 2004].

A discussion on the presence of wheeled vehicles in Cucuteni-Tripollye revolves around the interpretation of one type of zoomorphic figurines – those with horizontal holes in separate or integral legs (fig. 3,7) [Smirnova et al. 2018, 100, fig. 85]. It is assumed that clay wheels could have been fastened to the legs of these figurines [Gusev 1998]. But this series of zoomorphic figurines is very small, the parts were not found together *in situ*, wooden runners or stands could be attached to the figurines through holes in the legs. Attempts to prove the early appearance of wheeled transport through synchronization with the Funnelbeaker culture are dubious: the “earliest depiction of wagons” from Bronočice is unlikely to be such, rather representing a schematic sketch of a ‘landscape’ with houses [Palaguta 2022b]. The countdown can be started from the models of the Baden culture [Bondár 2012], already correlated with the end of the post-Trypillian period Tripollye CII, i.e. in fact, with the beginning of the Early Bronze Age, when two interconnected innovations were introduced at once: bronze alloys and wheels [Kozhin 2007].

Apparently, it was the presence of a bull sled with a sleigh that determined the ‘logistics’ of the Cucuteni-Tripollye culture and, accordingly, its de-

velopment strategy, based on the periodic moving of settlement sites. It allowed in a fairly short time to master the forest-steppe zone from the Eastern Carpathians to the Bug-Dnieper interfluvium, although the lack of a wheel limited these opportunities¹².

The migration was, evidently, realized according to the principle of successive settlement on a certain area, the basin of a small river or a section of a large river, along the banks of which a group of successively existing settlements was formed. Such development is usually accompanied by the periodic withdrawal of groups consisting of ‘extra’ youth from the main territory¹³.

More interesting chains of reasoning follow from the mobile settlement system. Firstly, it explains the absence of stable cult centres and the concentration of cult practices in the domestic context. This is probably why there are no grounds for using plastic objects as votives, known from ancient and medieval materials. Secondly, leaving dwellings with a set of ceramics, usual for Cucuteni-Tripollye, gets a rational basis as an additional and possible ritual practice; may be the limited logistics, the impossibility of moving significant loads using sledges provided the situation when it is more profitable to restart the production of ceramics on a new place than to transport objects from the abandoned village.

There remain a number of key issues in the reconstruction of the development of the settlement system. For example, the question of continuous or discontinuous dissemination, the presence of gaps between places of concentration of monuments close in time, possible boundaries of groups, the sequence of existence of settlements included in them. This requires a continuous study of the territories with the determination of the chronology of all discovered monuments. Despite the presence of several sets of monuments, the degree of exploration of the entire area remains different due to the localization of the main archaeological expeditions in the course of implementing certain projects¹⁴.

12. Long-distance migrations required widespread use of wheeled transport, such as the migration of the Helvetii described by Gaius Julius Caesar [Caes., Commentarii, I, 1-5].

13. According to the similar principle, for instance, the rite of *Ver Sacrum* was carried out among the Italians [Liv., Ab urbe condita, XXII, 9-10] or the withdrawal of Greek colonies.

14. In particular, such a picture was noted by E.G. Starkova in the course of mapping the monuments of Trypillia BII-CI.

11. A similar ‘drive’ of draft animals moved a threshing board in the neighboring Gumelnița culture on the Lower Danube [Skakun 2001].

What social structures could stand behind individual settlements, their local groups and variants? Classical sources testify to the formation of tribal unions in the form of 'six-polis' or 'twelve-polis' structures among the Ionian Greeks, Etruscans or Helvetians. The existence of such 'tribes' or 'unions', corresponding to local variants and groups, can also be assumed in Cucuteni-Tripollye. The difficulty of the area, however, is in fact that the system has changed dynamically. One of the grounds for revealing such links may be a comparison of ceramic assemblages: the degree of their similarity may reflect the density of ties between the population of settlements. Definitely, this requires the study of a whole group of settlements, and not just one monument, otherwise the next poorly substantiated hypotheses will arise, such as the idea of giant settlements as original centres of pilgrimage [Chapman, Gaydarska 2019; for criticism, see Palaguta 2021].

The issue of reconstructing the social structures of Cucuteni-Tripollye remains open. I.V. Manzura proposed a 'cultural-anthropological' scheme of its development, corresponding to the Schmidt-Passek periodization: 'time of priests', 'time of warriors', 'time of managers', 'chiefs' and 'patriarchs' [Manzura 2019].

Questions arise already from the interpretation of the initial period as 'time of priests'. The main argument pointing to the leading role of 'priests' is the pictorial elements in the form of 'snakes' in the ornamentation of ceramics, from which the idea of the important role of magic in this period develops, magic that required special clergymen [Manzura 2019, 25-27]. This is clearly not enough for social reconstruction.

Meanwhile, that stage, indeed, can be identified as a period of rapid spread of culture from the Carpathian region to the Bug-Dnieper interfluvium. Only a few fortifications have been identified; both circular and street planning of settlements existed. The close connection between the periphery and the centre is indicated with the fast dissemination of specific forms of ceramics, such as container vessels with decoration of vertical panels, which could have wooden prototypes [Palaguta 2016d]. Judging by the finds in Baia-În Muchie [Ursu, Aparaschivei 2014], they could be used to store some specific product (grain containers or beer containers?) in 'communal' or 'men's' houses. Ornamental schemes

based on 'snakes' play the role of a marker of cultural identity, but, at the same time, they were actively transformed, losing their pictorial character. The unity of ideological ideas is indicated with sets of 21 figurines that could depict ancestors and be used in mantic practice or in initiations.

The formation of local cultural variants, quite clearly outlined by the peculiarities of ceramics, is observed in the period Cucuteni A – Tripollye BI. Judging by the sharp increase in the number of fortifications and traces of armed conflicts (Druță I), military activity in the Cucuteni-Tripollye environment was really increasing at that moment. Ditches surround settlements not only in the most densely populated centre of the range, but also in peripheral areas, on the Southern Bug [Saile et al. 2021]. They were included in the 'cultural program' from the very beginning, and continued to exist in subsequent periods, where even traces of cannibalism were found [Haimovici 2003]. Thus, one can speak of the situationality of conflicts, but not that they lead to serious changes in social structures.

What forms of social organization could be shaped there? The relative uniformity of the collections of finds in buildings, recorded throughout the development of the culture, indicates that the hierarchy was not developed in that society. The existence of specialized buildings is a big question, although one can agree with D. Chernovol's assumption that some large constructions could function as 'men's houses' [Chernovol 2019, 10-11].

The basis of the spatial organization of the settlement was a circular layout. It has been formed already in the early period. During the Cucuteni A – Tripollye BI period, the construction of a layout from separate groups of dwellings organized in circular structures can be traced even in the cape fortified settlements (Hăbășești, Trușești). The further development of the circular planning principle was due both to the growth of settlements extending beyond the limits of narrow capes protected with ditches, and to the need to build the most compact circular scheme for the defense of overgrown settlements.

The ditches surrounding a village were also found on the giant settlements of the Tripollye BII-CI period [Palaguta 2021, 404, fig. 1]. The population of such villages reached several thousand. A similar number of inhabitants can be observed in the settlements of the Iroquois, Pueblo

or indigenous peoples of South America [Palaguta 2021, 411]. Judging by the standard interior layout and size of the houses (an analogy with a modern townhouse involuntarily arises), we get a picture of a relatively egalitarian society. Thanks to recent studies, pottery kilns were located along the perimeter of the building rings, possibly serving separate building sectors [Korvin-Piotrovsky, Ovchinnikov 2020], as well as some ‘megastructures’ in the form of a rectangular space fenced with adobe construction, part of which contains the remains of multi-level buildings. The idea of Trypillian ‘temples’ brings their interpretation to the sacred plane, beloved by many researchers, but here we are probably dealing with threshing grounds and barns for storing grain, which could be life support centres for ‘curias’ and living quarters. Their functioning, of course, included the cult and ritual side of life, which plays an important role in the life of any human community, but we should not forget about other functions of such structures: economic and social ones.

An important aspect that reflects the characteristics of the Cucuteni-Tripollye society is the absence of burials. A developed burial ritual with careful preservation of the remains, which indicates the presence of persistent vertical ties, is absent in this culture.

Such archaeologically fixed realities may correspond to the level of relatively egalitarian structures with a group hierarchy. They may correspond to an organization according to a system of age classes, similar to that which is still widespread among the pastoralists of East Africa, or male communities like the Melanesian ‘secret societies’, associations of male warriors among the American indigenous population, etc. Direct analogies, of course, are unacceptable here, but something similar is just possible at such level of development of material culture. The presence of such a paramilitary structure is clearly illustrated with a set of statuettes from the late Vinci settlement in Stublin [Palaguta 2018]. Such systems are dominated by horizontal connections, at the level of which the decision-making mechanism operates, while the number of such communities may well reach several thousand or tens of thousands of people [Berzkin 1995, 69-74].

Thus, referring to Cucuteni-Tripollye, one can speak more about the possible presence of ‘big

men’ than about ‘real chiefs’. The activity of ‘warriors’ is permanently traced throughout the development of the culture, and, unfortunately, no traces of ‘priests’ and ‘managers’ can be discerned in archaeological realities.

The basis of ideology at the initial stage of cultural development could be the myth of the unity of origin, through which the ties between communities were explained. An illustration for it, perhaps, was just a set of figurines: a dialogue with their ancestors-progenitors could well form the basis of scenes reproduced visually by arranging the figurines. A new line of representations is formed in the era of ‘giant settlements’, when the figurines are firmly linked with the house, but it can also be associated with the cult of ancestors [Diachenko, Chernovol 2007].

The depth of historical memory in similar pre-literate societies is relatively small: behind several generations of ‘visible’ ancestors, the space of myth, the *Dreamtimes*, begins. The system of representations is both stable, as far as *Dreamtimes* is concerned, and mobile, as far as local folklore is concerned. All this is reflected both in plastic and in ornaments, where a wide variability can be traced in the presence of a single base in the form of spiral motifs.

Conclusion

In my opinion, the problems both in the building of periodizations, the allocation of local groups of monuments, and in the analysis of ceramic assemblages, as well as in the interpretation of art objects lie in the fact that the sequence of research procedures is not always observed, there is no understanding of general processes in order to explain and explore through them private phenomena, and interpretation often runs ahead of formal and iconographic analysis.

As for periodization, the solution to the problem of ‘inconsistencies’ of the stages must be found in a conventional way. Here, the identification of the chronological sequence and genetic relationships between the settlements may well go hand in hand with the analysis of the series of radiocarbon dates [Harper et al. 2023].

The topic of social reconstructions is also one of the promising areas of research, especially if we start not from S. Žizek’s arguments about the “Big Other”, but take a closer look at possible ethno-

graphic and historical parallels. Of course, taking into account the fact that complete identity can never be found, some processes in different cultures proceed in a similar way. Although, at the same time, even within the development of one archaeological culture, communities of its bearers can take on various forms.

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